

THE USE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO IMPROVE CHILDREN'S LISTENING IN EFL CLASSES

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Annotation. The article discusses about the significance of implementation of authentic materials in order to improve children's listening comprehension in EFL (English as a foreign language) classes. The author examines diverse uses of authentic materials and provides relevant examples about the benefits of every single type.

Key words: videos, songs, rhymes, audiobooks, podcasts, stories, multimedia, extended learning.

Developing strong listening comprehension skills is a key component of English language acquisition, yet one of the most challenging for young learners. Traditional textbooks and classroom activities often provide only limited exposure to natural English as it is used in real-world contexts. To best prepare children for real-life encounters with English outside the classroom, teachers must incorporate authentic materials – resources produced for native speakers rather than language learners. Though more linguistically complex, authentic materials immerse children in colloquial speech patterns, accents, cultural references and expand their vocabulary through rich contexts [2]. When introduced strategically, authentic videos, audios, stories and songs significantly boost listening practice while maintaining engagement through interesting content. This article analyzes several types of effective authentic materials and provides suggestions for classroom implementation to maximize listening improvement.

Using Videos to Motivate Listening

Short video clips are powerful authentic resources that capture children's attention through visual and auditory stimulation. Sites like YouTube Kids offer myriad selections at varying levels to match different proficiency levels. Lower-level clips focus on basic conversational English through episodic cartoon segments while higher ones tackle fuller plots or documentaries. Before playing videos, teachers can prime students with targeted vocabulary or background knowledge to increase comprehension. During viewing, pausing allows questions and discussions to check understanding of key details. Afterward, follow-up creative activities further cement learning. Popular video options include Disney shorts, News4Kids segments, TED-Ed lessons and storybook adaptations teeming with descriptive language [5]. When implemented regularly and strategically, videos motivate and gradually enhance listening stamina and ability to glean implicit meaning.

Listening to Podcasts for Authentic Accents

While video engages multiple senses, audio-only mediums exercise children's listening concentration. Podcasts present ideal authentic resources for exposing learners to diverse, native English accents. Free podcasts like Stories for Kids provide entertaining narratives read aloud with clear enunciation at a natural pace, building familiarity with cadence, rhythm and pronunciation patterns. Teachers may choose episodes appropriate for proficiency levels and preview vocabulary beforehand. During playback, learners follow along visually and practice choral reading when paused. Quizzes afterward reinforce comprehension and generate motivation to tackle increasingly complex podcasts containing quicker speech, slang or dialects [4]. With regular short listening sessions, young learners gain comfort navigating more challenging authentic English delivered outside the classroom setting.

Using Stories to Comprehend Narrative Language

Storybooks offer rich linguistic contexts for developing narrative listening comprehension. While printed stories allow following along visually, audio

recordings of story readings deliver authentic prosody and expression. Teachers can obtain CDs and digital recordings of classics like "Freight Train" and "The Very Hungry Caterpillar" from pre-recorded story collections. Before listening, eliciting background knowledge and brainstorming vocabulary primes schema. Learners then follow along physically in the book while listening without images serves as a true auditory exercise. Repeated cycles of listening for specific comprehensible details followed by partner questioning fosters active engagement [7]. Meanwhile, total physical response (TPR) motions introduce figurative language and enable fuller immersion in story happenings [1]. Through repeated listenings of authentic story readings, children expand narrative listening abilities.

Using Songs to Practice Rhythm and Intonation

Children's songs provide an enjoyable way to tune into the melodic features of English through authentic musical recordings. Popular songs contain naturally exaggerated stress, intonation and rhythm to aid memorization while telling a story with vocabulary appropriate for young learners. Sources like YouTube and Spotify give access to professionally performed versions. Ahead of playback, previewing word meanings and discussing cultural contexts increases engagement. While listening actively with song sheets, learners follow along, repeating choruses and singing along gradually. After multiple exposures, they internalize proper stress and patterns through pleasure rather than stress [7]. Karaoke versions later invite braver students to sing solos with a teacher track playing simultaneously - boosting confidence navigating authentic pronunciation. Repeated exposure to authentic song recordings improves children's listening sensitivity to prosody.

Developing Listening through Interactive Audio Books

Digital audiobooks present an engaging way for children to experience authentic story language in an interactive format. Popular options like TumbleBooks include age-appropriate chapter books read by native English speakers with embedded features like animated illustrations, highlighted text and built-in quizzes. Before each session, teachers preview vocabulary and assistive

features. As the story plays, learners follow along visually, answering simple comprehension checks at intervals that pause playback. This balances challenge and success during listening. Options to rewind sections and adjust playback speed accommodate different abilities. Afterwards, students retell plot details or infer themes through extension activities. Repeated readings help internalize vocabulary through audio exposure more comprehensible than standardized tests [6]. Interactive books strengthen holistic listening skills.

Using Multimedia to Enrich Learning

Incorporating multiple modalities through carefully curated multimedia enhances learners' engagement with authentic materials. Combining songs, videos, audio stories and interactive elements in sequenced lessons builds foundational knowledge and linguistic familiarity. For example, an initial introduction uses videos to convey core concepts. Paired audio story readings offer supplemental auditory exposure. Interactive elements like quizzes and captioned lyrics check understanding before karaoke practice cements pronunciation. Follow-up project-based learning allows applying new vocabulary within authentic cultural contexts. Leveraging technology through varied activities ensures stimuli changes maintain focus while continually exposing students to comprehensible, authentic language. Chaining together multimedia resources cultivates more sophisticated listening skills over time [3].

Adapting Speed and Complexity to Proficiency Levels

A key consideration when using authentic materials in the classroom lies in selecting resources appropriate for learners' proficiency levels and carefully controlling variables like speed and complexity. For beginners, shorter extracts read more slowly provide increased processing time. Modifying texts by captioning difficult vocabulary aids comprehension and builds confidence. Exposing advanced students to more natural speech rates and verbatim recordings challenges them to infer unfamiliar words through wider contexts. Meanwhile, authentic materials become progressively more cognitively demanding over

months through sequencing. Sequenced listening loops recycle core vocabulary with enriched complexity each cycle. Gradual exposure paired with strategic scaffolding ensures continued engagement and motivation through balanced difficulty without risk of discouragement. By properly adapting authentic material variables, teachers optimize development of listening abilities.

Leveraging Authentic Materials through Extended Learning

Maximizing benefits from authentic listening practice requires extending lessons beyond classroom boundaries. Supplementary take-home materials like audio storybooks, podcast subscriptions and song lyric sheets provide opportunities for repeated extracurricular exposures. Students practice independently or with families - reinforcing classroom concepts in relaxed environments imperative for internalization. Discussion boards and audio journals invite describing personal reactions to authentic materials in English. Project assignments embed newly acquired vocabulary through written works, video demonstrations or community presentations. Capitalizing on technology, audio-taped personal recordings allow learners to share spoken responses analyzing plot points or opinions on cultural topics from listened resources. Extended learning builds initiative while deepening comprehension through personalized interactions with authentic language [5].

In summary, incorporating purposefully chosen, strategically implemented authentic materials presents an indispensable method for enhancing young EFL learners' listening comprehension development. Carefully adapting variables like speed and complexity to proficiency levels ensures continued motivation through balanced challenge. Combining modes through sequenced multimedia lessons exposes children to natural English through vivid, stimulating contexts. Most importantly, extending authentic practice beyond lessons through take-home assignments and personal interactive projects internalizes listening abilities applicable outside the classroom setting. When implemented judiciously, authentic resources offer immense potential to nurture sophisticated listening competency aligned with real-world English encounters.

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